

Plant Physiology and Biochemistry

PERIODICAL UV-B RADIATION HORMESIS IN BIOSYNTHESIS OF KALE SPROUTS NUTRACEUTICALS

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Research Paper
Section/Category:	UV-B; heat stress; salinity
Keywords:	Brassica oleracea var. sabellica; ultraviolet; germination; phenols; glucosinolates; antioxidant; abiotic stresses
Corresponding Author:	Francisco Artés-Hernández Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena: Universidad Politecnica de Cartagena Cartagena, Murcia SPAIN
First Author:	Noelia Castillejo
Order of Authors:	Noelia Castillejo Lorena Martínez-Zamora Francisco Artés-Hernández
Abstract:	<p>The objective of the present study was to evaluate the periodical UV-B radiation hormesis during kale seeds germination in their main secondary metabolite compounds content (phenols; glucosinolates; total antioxidant capacity – TAC–) and their changes during a refrigerated shelf-life. The total UV-B doses received were 0, 5, 10, and 15 kJ m⁻² (CTRL, UVB5, UVB10 and UVB15). UV was applied in days 3, 5, 7 and 10 with a 25% of the total dose. The morphological development of the sprouts was not affected by UV radiation. Phenolic content was positively affected by UVB10 and UVB15 treatments (>30 %). Likewise, TAC was increased by UV-B lighting ~10 % (DPPH) and ~20 % (FRAP). The hydroxycinnamic acid content in UVB15-treated sprouts increased by 52 %, while UVB5 reported an increase of 34 % in the kaempferol-3-diglucoside-7-glucoside concentration, compared to CTRL. After 10 d at 4°C of shelf-life, gallic acid hexoside I and gallic acid content were increased by 55 and 78 % compared to UV-untreated kale sprouts, respectively. Glucoraphanin was the main glucosinolate found in kale sprouts and seeds, followed by 4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin, whose biosynthesis was enhanced by UVB10 (~24 and ~27 %) and UVB15 (~36 and ~30 %), respectively, compared to CTRL. In conclusion, periodical low UV-B illumination represents a useful tool to stimulate phytochemicals biosynthesis in kale sprouts as an important source of bioactive compounds with potential health benefits.</p>
Suggested Reviewers:	<p>Victor H. Escalona University of Chile: Universidad de Chile vescalona@uchile.cl</p> <p>Daniel Jacobo-Velázquez Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey: Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey djacobov@itesm.mx</p> <p>Ariel R. Vicente CONICET La Plata arielvicente@agro.unlp.edu.ar</p>

UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE CARTAGENA

Postharvest and Refrigeration Group

Agronomical Engineering Faculty - ETSIA

Pº Alfonso XIII, 48. 30203 Cartagena. Murcia. SPAIN

fr.artes-hdez@upct.es

www.upct.es/gpostref

February 24th, 2021

Dear Editor:

I am pleased to submit our article '**PERIODICAL UV-B RADIATION HORMESIS IN BIOSYNTHESIS OF KALE SPROUTS NUTRACEUTICALS**'. The authors Noelia Castillejo, Lorena Martínez-Zamora, and I agree to its submission to the highly appreciated **Plant Physiology and Biochemistry**. This work is an original research carried out by the authors. All authors agree with the contents of the manuscript and its submission to this Journal. All Authors listed have significantly contributed to the work and agree to be in the author list. No part of the research has been published in any form elsewhere.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of discontinuous UV-B light during kale seeds germination in their main secondary metabolite compounds content and their changes during refrigerated shelf-life.

The novelty of this work lies on UV-B radiation hormesis in the biosynthesis of nutraceutical compounds while maintaining the optimum development of kale sprouts.

As main results, the morphological development of the sprouts was not affected by UV radiation. Phenolic content and total antioxidant capacity were positively affected by UV-B. The biosynthesis of the main glucosinolates found was enhanced up to 36 % regarding CTRL.

In conclusion, periodical UV-B light stimulates phytochemical biosynthesis in kale sprouts as an important source of bioactive compounds with potential health benefits.

Furthermore, the industrial relevance of the present study lies on the improvement of the nutritional quality of kale sprouts grown under periodical UV-B lighting. Since the consumers demand for functional foods able to improve their health, especially during the pandemic caused by SARS-COV 2, food industry has focused on looking for new techniques to improve the biosynthesis of phytochemicals, such as phenolic compounds and glucosinolates. In fact, periodical low UV-B doses during kale seeds sprouting have shown to increase the accumulation of bioactive compounds while maintaining the optimum development of the sprouts.

We hope that you agree on the merits and appropriateness of this study for publication in this journal.

Thank you and we look forward to your comments.

Sincerely,

Prof. Dr. Francisco Artés Hernández

Head of Postharvest and Refrigeration Group

Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena

P. Alfonso XIII, 48. E-30203 Cartagena. Murcia. SPAIN

Phone +34 968 32 55 09

Fax +34 968 32 54 33

Brassica olearacea var. *sabellica*

Accumulation and biosynthesis of secondary metabolites

HIGHLIGHTS

- UV-B light did not affect the sprouting parameters in kale
- UV-B enhanced up to 20 % the total antioxidant activity of kale sprouts
- UV-B increased up to 30 % the total and individual phenolic content of kale sprouts
- 10 and 15 kJ m⁻² UV-B stimulated the glucoraphanin and glucobrassicin synthesis by 30 %
- 10 and 15 kJ m⁻² UV-B are recommended to improve phytochemical content

PERIODICAL UV-B RADIATION HORMESIS IN BIOSYNTHESIS OF KALE SPROUTS NUTRACEUTICALS

Noelia Castillejo, Lorena Martínez-Zamora, Francisco Artés-Hernández*

Department of Agronomical Engineering & Institute of Plant Biotechnology, Universidad Politécnica
de Cartagena, Cartagena, Murcia, 30203, Spain.

* To whom correspondence should be addressed: Tel: +34-968-325509; E-mail: fr.artes-
hdez@upct.es. <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-0689-7301>.

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ABSTRACT

1 The objective of the present study was to evaluate the periodical UV-B radiation hormesis during
2 kale seeds germination in their main secondary metabolite compounds content (phenols;
3 glucosinolates; total antioxidant capacity – TAC–) and their changes during a refrigerated shelf-life.
4 The total UV-B doses received were 0, 5, 10, and 15 kJ m⁻² (CTRL, UVB5, UVB10 and UVB15).
5 UV was applied in days 3, 5, 7 and 10 with a 25% of the total dose. The morphological development
6 of the sprouts was not affected by UV radiation. Phenolic content was positively affected by UVB10
7 and UVB15 treatments (>30 %). Likewise, TAC was increased by UV-B lighting ~10 % (DPPH) and
8 ~20 % (FRAP). The hydroxycinnamic acid content in UVB15-treated sprouts increased by 52 %,
9 while UVB5 reported an increase of 34 % in the kaempferol-3-diglucoside-7-glucoside concentration,
10 compared to CTRL. After 10 d at 4°C of shelf-life, gallic acid hexoside I and gallic acid content were
11 increased by 55 and 78 % compared to UV-untreated kale sprouts, respectively. Glucoraphanin was
12 the main glucosinolate found in kale sprouts and seeds, followed by 4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin, whose
13 biosynthesis was enhanced by UVB10 (~24 and ~27 %) and UVB15 (~36 and ~30 %), respectively,
14 compared to CTRL. In conclusion, periodical low UV-B illumination represents a useful tool to
15 stimulate phytochemicals biosynthesis in kale sprouts as an important source of bioactive compounds
16 with potential health benefits.

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41 **Keywords:** *Brassica oleracea* var. *sabellica*, ultraviolet, germination, phenols, glucosinolates,
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1. INTRODUCTION

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2 Nowadays, society lifestyle tends to improve consumer habits introducing healthier foods rich in
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4 bioactive compounds content. In this way, the consumption of functional foods enriched in
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6 phytochemicals, most of them obtained from fruit and vegetables, has increased in last twenty years
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8 (Shahidi & Ambigaipalan, 2015). As a consequence, the consumption, and therefore its production,
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10 of ready-to-eat vegetables harvested in the early growth stages of the plant, commonly known as
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12 sprouts seeds, has exponentially increased, because of their convenience, nutritional profile, health
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14 benefits and lack of additives (Benincasa et al., 2019).
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19 In fact, a daily consumption of more than 500 g of fruit and vegetables has been associated with a
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21 reduction of risk factors for chronic diseases, such as diabetes, obesity or cardiovascular diseases
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23 (Fernandes et al., 2018). These healthy effects are related to the presence of bioactive compounds,
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25 such as carotenoids, glucosinolates (GLs), vitamins, minerals, and phenolic compounds, which have
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27 exhibited important biological properties (Barba et al., 2017). Indeed, these phytochemical
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29 compounds have demonstrated to have an essential role in cancer prevention and oxidation or
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31 inflammatory reactions (Klug et al., 2018; Martínez-Hernández et al., 2013).
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37 *Brassica oleracea* var. *sabellica*, commonly known as kale, has been used in the present study as a
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39 model of a germinated seed. Vegetables from the *Brassica* family are rich in antioxidant compounds,
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41 especially phenolics and GLs. Besides, sprouts and young plants from Brassicas have resulted to
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43 contain 10-fold more bioactive compounds than mature plants (Šamec et al., 2018). For this reason,
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45 edible sprouts and new technologies to improve their phytochemical compounds are a hot topic of
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47 study.
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52 Light has the most important role in plant development, providing not only the main source of energy
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54 for photosynthesis, but also the signal for a multitude of physiological responses. Light quality
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56 (wavelength), quantity (intensity), photoperiod (duration), and uniform direction are key components
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58 of light conditions, which affect to plant morphology and secondary metabolite content (Pennisi et
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al., 2019). Ultraviolet (UV) and blue radiations of the electromagnetic spectrum, whose wavelength varies from 100 to 400 nm are responsible of directing the photosynthetic reaction and regulating the opening of the stomas (Taulavuori et al., 2018).

Light treatments using adequate doses of UV-B (280-320 nm) can act as an important regulator of secondary metabolites production in plants, such as phenolic compounds, carotenoids, and GLs (Moreira-Rodríguez et al., 2017a). In fact, the oxidative stress produced by continuous exposure to UV-B can led the accumulation and synthesis of several antioxidant enzymes and secondary metabolites, such as ascorbic acid, β -carotene, flavonoids, GLs and some alkaloids that help to neutralise the impact of oxidative stress (Moreira-Rodríguez et al., 2017a). According to Moreira-Rodríguez et al., (2017b), GL accumulation was 75 % increased after 24 h UV-B treatment (24.05 kJ m⁻² dose) in 7-day broccoli sprouts. In the same study, this UV-B dose also reported an enhancement of the biosynthesis some phenolic glycosides, such as 5-sinapoylquinic acid by 121 %. Nevertheless, the application of high doses of UV-B radiation results harmful to plants producing important damages on proteins, lipids, membranes and DNA (Artés et al., 2009). Therefore, an optimized dose should be found in each case to preserve from UV damages while stimulating the synthesis of bioactive compounds. From the best of our knowledge, the research of the optimal dose which could be applied periodically during kale sprouts growth to enhance the phytochemical compounds have been developed evaluating also UV-B effects on their nutritional quality. In this way, the periodically UV-B treatments can be implemented in sprout industry.

The main aim of the present study was to evaluate the effect of kale seeds germination under periodical application of low UV-B doses in the main phytochemicals content (GLs, phenols and total antioxidant capacity) and their changes during refrigerated shelf-life as a minimally processed product.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Plant material used and growing conditions

Kale seeds (*Brassica olearacea* var. *sabellica*) were supplied by Intersemillas S.A. (Valencia, Spain).

Two g of kale seeds were weighed and disinfected with a fungicide for 10 min (Geoxe 50 WG - Fludioxonil 50 % w/w -; Syngenta). Subsequently, two 1 min rinses were carried out with autoclaved distilled water and seeds were left water submerged for 18 h in darkness. In a laminar flow hood (Telstar Bio-II-A/M, Japan), the kale seeds were disposed in polypropylene trays (170 x 120 x 50 mm), using a filter paper layer moistened with sprayed autoclaved distilled water as a support. To ensure a high relative humidity (RH) the trays were covered with a 40 µm oriented polypropylene film. Kale seeds were germinated in a growth chamber (Sanyo MLR-350 H, Japan) for 10 d at 20 °C and 90 % RH.

2.2. UV-B treatments

UV-B treatments were applied during germination on days 3, 5, 7 and 10 with a 25 % of the total dose received which was based on previous experiences of our Research Group and on those recommended by Formica-Oliveira et al. (2017b).

The radiation chamber consisted of a reflective stainless-steel chamber with 2 lamp banks being fitted to each bank 6 UV-B unfiltered emitting lamps (TL 40W/01 RS; Philips, Eindhoven, The Netherlands). It was also provided with a ventilator to renovate the air from inside of the chamber (Formica-Oliveira et al., 2017b). Kale sprouts were placed between the two lines of lamps at 17.5 cm above and below on a polystyrene net. The UV-B intensity applied ($7.99 \pm 0.40 \text{ W m}^{-2}$) was calculated as the mean of 20 readings on each side of the net by using a UV radiometer (LP 471 UVB, Delta OHM, Italy). The light intensities were kept constant and the applied doses were varied by altering the exposure time at the fixed distance. UV-B treatments applied were the following:

- **CTRL:** No UV radiation was our control treatment.
- **UVB5:** the sprouts received at the end of the germination process 5 kJ m^{-2} UV-B in 4 equal applications of $1.25 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ conducted on days 3, 5, 7 and 10.
- **UVB10:** the sprouts received at the end of the germination process 10 kJ m^{-2} UV-B in 4 equal applications of $2.50 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ conducted on days 3, 5, 7 and 10.

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- **UVB15**: the sprouts received at the end of the germination process 15 kJ m^{-2} UV-B in 4 equal applications of $3.25 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ conducted on days 3, 5, 7 and 10.

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The UV-B dose was selected based on our previous experiments and the data reported by Formica-Oliveira et al. (2017b) in order to obtain maximum phytochemicals synthesis while minimizing heating and evaporation processes during treatment, which may affect the quality of the product. After 1 h from the end of the UV-B application, samples were immediately frozen at $-80 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until they were freeze-dried (Lyoquest-85, Telstar Technologies, Terrassa, Spain) and kept at that temperature until the analytical determinations were performed.

2.3. Minimal processing operations

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Just after 1 h the last UV treatment conducted after 10 d of germination at $20 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the sprouts were hand harvested and disinfected in a cold room at $5 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a sodium hypochlorite solution (1 min; 150 ppm; $5 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; pH=6.5) and then rinsed 1 min in water at $5 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Kale sprouts were placed in 250 mL polypropylene closed containers (10 x 8 x 3.5 cm) under 90-95 % RH and atmospheric gas partial pressures up to 10 d at $4 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Samples were collected for analysed on days 4, 7, and 10 of the refrigerated shelf-life.

2.4. Analyses and determinations

2.4.1. Sprouts growth parameters

The sprouts were horizontally disposed nearby a ruler and photographed. The length of the hypocotyl (H) and root (R) of 3 replicates of 10 sprouts from each treatment, and on each sampling day, was determined using the ImageJ program (Wayne Rasband, Maryland, USA). Results were presented in cm. Growth speed was calculated by dividing H (mm) by the growing days and presented in mm d^{-1} .

2.4.2. Extraction of phytochemical compounds from samples

A volume of 3 mL methanol:water (80:20, v/v) were added to 25 mg of freeze-dried sprouts. The samples were vigorously shaken an orbital shaker (Stuart, Stone, UK) for 1 h inside a polystyrene box in darkness with an ice bed. The extracts were centrifuged at 3,220 g for 10 min at $5 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The supernatant

was recovered for Total Phenolic Content (TPC), Total Antioxidant Capacity (TAC), and individual phenolic content analyses.

The extraction of GLs was performed according to Moreira-Rodríguez et al., (2017b) with slight modifications. Briefly, a sample of 0.2 ± 0.01 g of kale sprouts powder were placed in glass tubes and 10 mL of ethanol/water (70:30, v/v) previously heated at 70 °C in a bath. As internal standard (IS) was used 50 µL of 3 mM sinigrin. Samples were incubated at 70 °C for 30 min and vortexed at 0, 10, and 20 min to ensure myrosinase inactivation. After that, the extracts were rapidly cooled on an ice bath and centrifuged at $18,000 \times g$ for 10 min at 4 °C (L-90K Ultracentrifuge Beckman Coulter, rotor type 45 70Ti). The supernatant was collected for GLs analysis. Just after the extraction, GLs were desulphated and purified using disposable polypropylene columns (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The preparation of columns was carried out by adding 500 µL of MilliQ water, followed by 500 µL of Sephadex A-25 and 500 µL of MilliQ water. Then, 3 mL of ethanolic extract were added into a prepared column and allowed to drip through slowly. After that, two aliquots of 500 µL of MilliQ water were added followed by others two of 500 µL of 0.02 M sodium acetate. Purified sulfatase (75 µL) was added to each sample and left at room temperature overnight (16 h). Finally, 1.25 mL of water were added into columns to recover desulfoglucosinolates and the extracts were kept at -80 °C until analysis.

2.4.3. Total phenolic content.

TPC was determined following the method described by Singleton and Rossi, (1965). Briefly, 19 µL sample extract were placed on a 96-well plate (Greiner Bio-One; Frickenhausen, Germany) and 29 µL of 1 mol L^{-1} Folin–Ciocalteu reagent were added. After 3 min incubation in darkness at room temperature (RT), 192 µL of 0.4 % Na_2CO_3 2 % NaOH were added. The absorbance was measured at 750 nm using a microplate reader (Tecan Infinite M200, Männedorf, Switzerland) after 1 h incubation in darkness at RT. The TPC was expressed as g chlorogenic acid equivalents (CAE) kg^{-1} dw. Each sample was analysed in triplicate.

2.4.4. Individual phenolic content

1 A sample of 1 mL of the methanolic extract was filtered using 0.2 μm PTFE membrane filters. Analysis
2 and identification of individual phenolic compounds were based on Castillejo et al. (2021). An Ultra
3 High Performance Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC) instrument (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped
4 with a DGU-20A degasser, LC-30AD quaternary pump, SIL-30AC autosampler, CTO-10AS column
5 heater, and SPD-20A photodiode array detector was used. Chromatographic analyses were carried
6 out into a Gemini C18 column (250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size; Phenomenex, Torrance CA,
7 USA). Identified phenolic compounds are shown in Figure 1. The results were expressed as g gallic
8 acid equivalents kg^{-1} dw for gallic acid hexoside I and gallic acid; as g chlorogenic acid equivalents kg^{-1}
9 kg^{-1} dw for 3-O-caffeoylquinic acid, 4-O-caffeoylquinic acid, 5-O-caffeoylquinic acid, and 1,2-diferuloyl-
10 gentobiose; as mg caffeic acid equivalents kg^{-1} dw for caffeic acid and caffeic acid derivative; as g
11 hydroxycinnamic acid equivalents kg^{-1} dw for hydroxycinnamic acid; and as g rutin equivalents kg^{-1}
12 dw for kaempferol-3-diglucoside-7-glucoside and kaempferol-3-sinapoyl-7-diglucoside. Each sample
13 was analysed in triplicate.

30 2.4.5. Total antioxidant capacity

31 TAC was analysed by using two different methods described by Castillejo et al. (2021): DPPH (2,2-
32 diphenyl-1-picryl-hydrazyl-hydrate free radical method) and FRAP (Ferric Reducing Antioxidant
33 Power) assays. For DPPH assay, 194 μL of DPPH (0.7 mM) solution were added to 21 μL of sprout
34 extract. The mixture was incubated for 30 min at RT in darkness. The TAC by DPPH was measured by
35 changes in absorbance at 515 nm. FRAP method was carried out using a daily reaction solution (10:1:1;
36 v/v/v) containing sodium acetate buffer (pH 3.6), 10 mM TPTZ solution (in 40 mM HCl), and 20 mM
37 FeCl_3 and incubated at 37 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h in darkness. Then, 198 μL of FRAP solution were added to 6 μL
38 of methanolic extract and incubated for 14 min at RT in darkness. The TAC by FRAP was measured
39 by changes in absorbance at 593 nm. The results were expressed as g of Trolox Equivalents (TE) kg^{-1}
40 dw. Each sample was analysed in triplicate.

57 2.4.6. Glucosinolates content

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Analysis and identification of GLs were conducted according to Moreira-Rodríguez et al., (2017b) with slight modifications. An UHPLC (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a DGU-20A degasser, LC-30AD quaternary pump, SIL-30AC autosampler, CTO-10AS column heater, and SPD-20A photodiode array detector was used. Chromatographic analyses were carried out into a Gemini C18 column (250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 µm particle size; Phenomenex, Torrance CA, USA). Separation of desulfoglucosinolates in the UHPLC system was achieved using water (phase A) and acetonitrile (phase B) as mobile phases. A flow rate of 1.5 mL min⁻¹ and a gradient of 0/100, 28/80, 30/100 (min/% phase A) with an injection volume of 20 µL was performed. Desulfoglucosinolates were detected at 227 nm and identified compounds are shown in Figure 2. Obtained data were expressed as g glucoraphanin kg⁻¹ dw. Each sample was extracted and analysed in triplicate.

2.5. Statistical analyses

The experiment was a two-factor (treatment × time) design subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Statgraphics Plus software (v. 5.1. Statpoint Technologies. Inc. Warrenton. VA. USA). Statistical significance was assessed at the level p<0.05, and Tukey's multiple range test was used to separate means.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Effect of UV-B radiation on kale sprouts growth

The main growth parameters during 10 d at 20 °C under several UV-B doses are presented in Table 1. Kale sprouts were harvested when they reached an average hypocotyl and sprout length of 2.94 ± 0.31 cm and 5.06 ± 0.51 cm, respectively. In general, UV-B did not influence the hypocotyl and sprout length development. After 10 d at 20 °C, the H/R Ratio was 1.42 ± 0.20 without differences between treatments. The FW/DW Ratio of 3-day kale sprouts was 2.45 ± 0.01, which increased at the end of the sprouting period in UV-B treated samples up to 11.97 ± 0.27, reporting a 127 % increase compared to CTRL samples (5.27 ± 1.20). In addition, the growth speed after 5 d was 53 % higher on UVB10 and UVB15 samples, and an increase of 17 % was registered after 7 d in UVB10-treated

kale sprouts compared to CTRL samples. No differences were found among the remaining treatments on days 3 and 10 of the sprouting period.

These results reveal that plants under UV-B lighting can develop specific photomorphogenic responses, which results in an increase of the length of the kale hypocotyls (Escobar-Bravo et al., 2017). In fact, as appreciated in Table 1, plant growth is partially inhibited by UV-B lighting, as recently described by Dou et al. (2019) and Lim et al. (2020). This effect can be justified by the fact that UVB-resistance 8 receptors are able to trigger a specific response to inhibit the hypocotyl elongation (Tohge et al., 2011; Yadav et al., 2020) and, subsequently, the growth of the kale sprouts. In addition, UV-B light quantity and quality has demonstrated to increase the temperature and stress conditions in plants, which can explain the reduction of sprout length of UV-B kale sprouts compared to the CTRL treatment (Escobar-Bravo et al., 2017).

3.2.Effect of UV-B radiation on the phenolic content

The phenolic content of the UV-B treated, and untreated kale sprouts was totally and individually analysed, as well as its relation to the TAC.

TPC results obtained by the Folin-Ciocalteu method are presented in Figure 3. The TPC of kale seeds was 3.8 ± 0.4 g chlorogenic acid kg^{-1} dw, which was increased 4.5-fold after 10 d of sprouting at 20°C in darkness (2.8 g chlorogenic acid kg^{-1} dw). After 10 d of shelf-life period at 4 °C as a fresh-cut product, the TPC was enhanced 35 % in CTRL kale sprouts compared to its amount at harvest. However, kale sprouts under UV-B treatments reported significant increases in the TPC compared to CTRL samples, both during growing and postharvest periods. Indeed, during germination, all studied UV-B doses reported an increase of 22 % compared to CTRL. At harvest (after 10 growing d), UVB5, UVB10, and UVB15 had 26, 39, and 32 % higher concentration in TPC as regards CTRL, respectively. This tendency was also maintained during the postharvest shelf-life, being the TPC 30, 33, and 35 % increased by 5, 10, and 15 kJ m^{-2} UV-B doses, respectively.

1 These results showed a protective response carried out by the plant to protect itself from adverse
2 environmental factors such as the radiation of very short wavelength of the light spectra, like the UV-
3 B radiation. In this way, discontinuous treatments of 1.5 W m^{-2} UV-B for 1 h in 5-day peanut sprouts
4 (each growing day) increased the TPC by 11.1 % in comparison to untreated peanut sprouts (Nguyen
5 et al., 2020).
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10 As Figure 1 and Table 2 show, eleven major phenolic compounds were identified in kale sprouts,
11 including (1) Gallic acid hexoside I, (2) Gallic acid, (3) 3-O-caffeoylquinic acid, (4) 4-O-
12 caffeoylquinic acid, (5) 5-O-caffeoylquinic acid, (6) 1,2-diferuloyl-gentobiose, (7) caffeic acid, (8)
13 caffeic acid derivative, (9) hydroxycinnamic acid, (10) Kaempferol-3-diglucoside-7-glucoside, and
14 (11) Kaempferol-3-sinapoyl-7-diglucoside.
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24 UV-B significantly induced the accumulation of nine of the eleven identified compounds (Table 2).
25 Only 3-O-caffeoylquinic acid and 1,2-diferuloyl-gentobiose were not stimulated by discontinuous
26 UV-B preharvest treatments. Of these stimulated compounds, kaempferol-3-diglucoside-7-glucoside
27 was the major flavonoid found, followed by hydroxycinnamic acid, as the major phenolic acid
28 identified in kale sprouts. This fact has been also shown by Duarte-Sierra et al. (2020), who reported
29 an increase of hydroxyl-cinnamic acids after UVB radiation (1.5 and 7.5 kJ m^{-2}) on broccoli florets.
30 Particularly, UVB10 was the main inductor of the biosynthesis of the rest of identified phenolics
31 compounds, although all the UV-B doses positively affected to the concentration of these
32 nutraceuticals.
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46 From a different point of view, 3-O-caffeoylquinic acid was the predominant phenolic compound
47 found in kale seeds. In fact, its concentration decreased 12.6-fold after 10 d of sprouting at $20 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in
48 darkness. Besides, no differences were found from the 7th growing d to the end of the shelf-life period
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57 In contrast, hydroxycinnamic acid, as the main phenolic acid, and kaempferol-3-diglucoside-7-
58 glucoside, as the predominant flavonoid found in kale sprouts, increased their concentration during
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germination by 4 and 16-fold compared to kale seeds, respectively. Such accumulation was also maintained during the postharvest storage. Focus on these compounds, the hydroxycinnamic acid content was increased in all UV treatments assayed. In fact, UVB5 and UVB10 treatments reported the higher content at harvest, with 16 and 13 % increases compared to CTRL. On the 4th d of the shelf-life period, the concentration of the hydroxycinnamic acid reached 4.37 ± 0.24 g kg⁻¹ dw in UVB15 kale sprouts, which is 52 % higher than that found in CTRL. Similarly, UVB5 reported an increase of 34 % on the kaempferol-3-diglucoside-7-glucoside content, compared to CTRL. Nevertheless, UVB10 and UVB15 showed 27 and 33 % higher content than CTRL, respectively. Those values were preserved until the end of the shelf-life period assayed.

Furthermore, the minor phenolic compounds content was highly enhanced after discontinuous UV-B radiation. For instance, at the end of the postharvest storage, gallic acid hexoside I content of UV-B treatments reported an increase of 55 %, while gallic acid content increased by 78 % compared to CTRL kale sprouts. A similar behaviour was also shown in the caffeic acid and its derivatives content, as well as the kaempferol derivatives.

Regarding the obtained results, it is known that UV-B induces genes involved in the phenylpropanoid biosynthesis pathway (Jenkins, 2009; Morales et al., 2010). In fact, when UV light is absorbed, bioactive compounds as flavonoids, hydroxycinnamic acids, and other phenolic compounds act as UV penetration reducers into the plant tissue to protect the plant from damage caused by ROS (Jenkins, 2009; Morales et al., 2010; Solovchenko and Merzlyak, 2008).

In fact, UV-B illumination, as an abiotic elicitor, is a good strategy to induce physiological changes and stimulate defense or stress-induced responses in plants. This kind of UV treatments trigger the synthesis of phytochemical compounds in young plants and vegetables during sprouting. This tendency agrees with Formica-Oliveira et al. (2017a), who studied the effect of the application of UV-B on the biosynthesis of phenolic compounds in fresh-cut carrots. Indeed, fresh-cut carrots treated with UV-B (1.5 kJ m⁻²) reached a content of phenolic compounds 120 % higher than untreated samples.

1 Furthermore, Moreira-Rodríguez et al. (2017a) showed an increase of gallic acid hexoside II (35.1
2 %) in broccoli sprouts treated with a unique dose of 7.16 W m^{-2} UV-B for 120 min (51.55 kJ m^{-2}).
3 However, in the same study, the combination of UV-B lighting and $25 \mu\text{M}$ methyl jasmonate reported
4 notable increases in the accumulation of phenolic compounds. Similarly, Moreira-Rodríguez et al.
5 (2017b) reported increases in sinapoyl malate (12 %), gallotannic acid (48 %), and 5-sinapoyl-quinic
6 acid (121 %) content in broccoli sprouts exposed for 120 min to 3.34 W m^{-2} UV-B (24.05 kJ m^{-2}).
7 These studies concluded that the biosynthesis of phenolic compounds was enhanced by low
8 intensities, while it was inhibited by high intensities in Brassica sprouts. Such results justify applying
9 the periodical application of low UV-B intensities during kale sprouting, as we did in our study.
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21 **3.3.Effect of UV-B radiation on the antioxidant activity**

22 As it is widely known, the biosynthesis of phenolic compounds is directly related to the TAC of foods.
23 The TAC of UV-B treated kale sprouts are presented in Figure 4. DPPH values of CTRL kale sprouts
24 at harvest increased by 142 % in comparison to seeds, which was increased up to 25 % during the
25 first 4 d of the refrigeration storage period and subsequently decreased to the initial values found at
26 harvest (Figure 4.A).
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37 Moreover, the application of 5 kJ m^{-2} UV-B increased the TAC by 28 % compared to CTRL at harvest,
38 while no differences were found between UVB10, UVB15, and CTRL samples. In a similar way,
39 UV-B radiation enhanced the TAC during the postharvest period. Indeed, after 4 d at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ UVB10
40 and UVB15 showed 8 % higher ability to scavenge DPPH radicals compared to CTRL and UVB5.
41 Nevertheless, at the end of the shelf-life period, UVB5, UVB10, and UVB15 showed an increase by
42 13, 11, and 6 % on the TAC compared to CTRL.
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52 From other point of view, a different behaviour was appreciated in Figure 4.B regarding the TAC
53 measured by the FRAP assay. FRAP values at harvest of CTRL kale sprouts increased by 250 %
54 compared to seeds. In this case, the TAC increased by 62 % after 10 d of storage at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in comparison
55 with kale sprouts at harvest.
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1 From a general overview, all the UV-B treatments applied during growing were able to increase the
2 iron reduction capacity of kale sprouts throughout the study. For instance, after 10 d growing, UVB5,
3 UVB10, and UVB15 kale sprouts showed 28, 20, and 23 % higher TAC measured by FRAP than
4 CTRL, respectively. Besides, on the first analyses of the refrigeration period, UVB10 and UVB15
5 presented an increase by 21 and 30 % on the 4th d, respectively, and by 21 % on the 7th d compared
6 to the CTRL in both cases. Similarly, on the 10th d of the postharvest period, UVB5 showed an
7 increase by 8 % compared to CTRL, while UVB10 did it by 12 %.

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16 In a similar manner, Tsurunaga et al. (2013) reported increases of 1.6-fold in the scavenging capacity
17 against DPPH free radicals in 6-day buckwheat sprouts treated with 10 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for 24 h (187.5
18 kJ m^{-2}) UV-B in comparison to sprouts kept in dark. Besides, the TAC was higher in the postharvest
19 period compared to the germination process, as it has been appreciated in the present study. Similarly,
20 broccoli florets exposed to 2 kJ m^{-2} UV-B reported an increase in the TAC after 6 and 18 h compared
21 to the initial values at harvest (Darré et al., 2017), which also explained that abiotic stresses provoked
22 by UV-B are able to increase the TAC in different stages of the plant development. Therefore, the
23 described results have suggested that UV-B illumination is a valuable technological strategy to induce
24 the TAC of minimally processed sprouts.

39 **3.4.Effect of UV-B radiation on the glucosinolate content**

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42 Eight major GL compounds were identified in kale sprouts: (1) Glucoiberin, (2) Progoitrin, (3)
43 Glucoraphanin, (4) 4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin, (5) Glucoerucin, (6) Glucobrassicin, (7) 4-methoxy-
44 glucobrassicin, and (8) Neoglucobrassicin (Figure 2 and Table 3). In general, glucoraphanin was the
45 GL found in a greater proportion in kale sprouts and seeds, followed by 4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin
46 (Figure 2). Indeed, the total GL content of CTRL kale sprouts at harvest after 10 growing d was 125.9
47 $\pm 1.4 \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ dw}$, Glucoraphanin content was the 26 % and 4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin the 23 % of the
48 total content.

1 The individual and total GLs content, quantified as desulfoglucosinolates, was positively affected by
2 UV-B treatments. In fact, the content of some desulfoglucosinolates compounds was highly
3 accentuated, such as glucoiberin and glucoraphanin, as aliphatic GLs, and 4-methoxy-glucobrassicin
4 and neoglucobrassicin, as indolyl GLs. Nevertheless, the amount of progoitrin, 4-hydroxy-
5 glucobrassicin, glucoerucin and glucobrassicin was not increased by discontinuous UV-B
6 applications during the growth of kale sprouts.
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12 The total GLs content started to increase from the first UV-B dose applied on the 3rd d of the growing
13 period in darkness. In this way, the maximum amount was reached after 7 d at 20 °C, when UVB5,
14 UVB10, and UVB15 treatments increased their synthesis of GLs by 32, 42, and 39 %, respectively,
15 compared to CTRL. Similarly, on the 7th d of the postharvest period at 4 °C, UVB5, UVB10, and
16 UVB15 reported 18, 21, and 18 % more GLs accumulation compared to CTRL, respectively.
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26 Among the aliphatic GLs, glucobeirin content was increased by all the UV-B treatments during both
27 preharvest and postharvest periods. However, UVB10-treated kale sprouts reported an increase at
28 harvest by 58 % as regards the CTRL treatment. In contrast, after 10 d at 4 °C of shelf-life, UVB15
29 increased by 26 % the accumulation of glucoiberin in comparison to CTRL. Glucoraphanin content
30 was also increased in a similar way as previously described. In fact, UVB10 and UVB15 reported at
31 the end of the shelf-life period a higher content by 24 and 36 % compared to CTRL, respectively.
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42 Among the indolyl GLs, UVB10 and UVB15 kale sprouts presented at harvest an increase of 27 and
43 30 % of their content in 4-methoxy-glucobrassicin, respectively. Both treatments also increased the
44 content on neoglucobrassicin by 31 % compared to CTRL. After that, the indolyl GLs amount slightly
45 decreased during the shelf-life period at 4°C. Nevertheless, it should be emphasized that on the 7th d
46 of shelf-life, the accumulation of 4-methoxy-glucobrassicin was increased by 30, 120, and 29 % on
47 UVB5, UVB10 and UVB15 kale sprouts, respectively. Neoglucobrassicin experimented an increase
48 of 93, 89, and 100 % on the same treatments as regards the CTRL, respectively.
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1 The obtained results show that the GL content was increased in UV-B treated kale sprouts. In fact,
2 previous authors agree with this behaviour. Moreira-Rodríguez et al. (2017a) showed an increase of
3 glucoraphanin (78 %) and 4-methoxy-glucobrassicin (177 %) in 7-day broccoli sprouts treated with
4 7.16 W m⁻² UV-B for 120 min (51.55 kJ m⁻²), which had a synergistic effect in combination with 25
5 µM methyl jasmonate. In the same way, Moreira-Rodríguez et al. (2017b) reported the highest GL
6 accumulation in 7-day broccoli sprouts after 24 h 3.34 W m⁻² UV-B treatment for 120 min (24.05 kJ
7 m⁻²). Indeed, that treatment increased by 170, 78, and 73 % the biosynthesis of 4-methoxy-
8 glucobrassicin, glucobrassicin, and glucoraphanin, respectively.
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10 Furthermore, these results also agree with Mewis et al. (2012), who showed as UV-B radiation
11 enhanced the biosynthesis of GLs, mainly 4-methoxy-glucobrassicin and glucoraphanin in 12-day
12 broccoli sprouts 24 h after 0.3 and 0.9 kJ m⁻² doses. Indeed, this exposure triggered the transcription
13 of several genes (CYP71A and CYP71B families of Cyt P450 monooxygenases) related to GLs
14 biosynthetic pathway. Likewise, FMO GS-OX5, involved in the oxidation of methylthioalkyl GLs
15 into methylsulfinylalkyl GLs, which triggered the main pathway to the synthesis of aliphatic GLs
16 (glucobeirin and glucoraphanin). Besides, transcription factor MYB51 expression was also induced
17 by UV-B lighting, which also catalyzes the hydroxylation of 4-methoxy-glucobrassicin and
18 neoglucobrassicin, as main indolyl GLs identified in brassicas sprouts.
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41 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

42 Hormetic effects of UV-B radiation, periodically applied up to a total received dose of 15 kJ/m², did
43 not negatively affect the normal kale sprouts development, while in some cases it can speed the
44 sprouting process. Besides, the TPC was increased by application of a total dose of 10 or 15 kJ/m²
45 UV-B, applied with a 25 % of such dose on days 3, 5, 7 and 10 of the sprouting period at 20 °C in
46 darkness. The TAC was also increased by UV-B illumination by 10 and 20 %, measured by DPPH
47 and FRAP methods, respectively. UV-B also increased the main phenolic compounds content while
48 a total dose of 10 or 15 kJ/m² UV-B enhanced the biosynthesis of the main GL by ~30 % compared
49 to a UV-untreated CTRL.
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1 In conclusion, periodically low UV-B treatments while the seeds are sprouting could be a useful
2 technological tool to stimulate phytochemicals biosynthesis in kale sprouts, which were even
3 enhanced during a refrigerated shelf-life period as a minimally processed product. Accordingly, UV-
4 B treated sprouts will become an important source of bioactive compounds with great potential health
5 benefits for consumers.
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10 **DECLARATIONS**

11 **Author contributions statement**

12 Noelia Castillejo: Methodology; Formal analysis; Investigation; Writing – Original Draft. Lorena
13 Martínez-Zamora: Methodology; Formal analysis; Data curation; Investigation; Writing – Original
14 Draft. Francisco Artés–Hernández: Conceptualization; Resources; Writing – Review & Editing;
15 Supervision; Funding acquisition.
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28 **Funding statement**

29 Project financed by the Autonomous Community of the Region of Murcia nº 20849/PI/18 through the
30 grant call for projects for the development of scientific and technical research by competitive groups,
31 included in the Regional Programme for the Promotion of Scientific and Technical Research (Action
32 Plan 2018) of the Seneca Foundation - Science and Technology Agency of the Region of Murcia
33 (Spain).
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44 **Acknowledgements**

45 Noelia Castillejo was funded by a predoctoral grant (FPU16/04763) from the Spanish Ministry of
46 Education. Lorena Martínez-Zamora contract has been co-financed by the European Social Fund
47 (ESF) and the Youth European Initiative (YEI) under the Spanish Seneca Foundation
48 (21322/PDGI/19). The technical assistance of Francisca Andreo is highly appreciated.
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58 **Competing interest statement**

59 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.
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Table 1. Growth parameters of UV-B treated (CTRL; 5; 10, and 15 kJ m⁻²) kale sprouts during 10 growing d at 20 °C in darkness.

Growing days	Treatment	Hypocotyl length (cm)	Sprout length (cm)	H/R Ratio	FW/DW Ratio	Growth speed (mm d ⁻¹)
3	CTRL	0.71 ± 0.28 ^c	1.89 ± 0.53 ^c	0.58 ± 0.13 ^b	2.51 ± 0.01 ^{A b}	2.36 ± 0.93 ^a
	UVB5	0.85 ± 0.16 ^b	1.94 ± 0.22 ^c	0.78 ± 0.11 ^b	2.42 ± 0.01 ^{B d}	2.84 ± 0.53 ^{ab}
	UVB10	0.73 ± 0.13 ^c	2.18 ± 0.18 ^d	0.51 ± 0.10 ^c	2.43 ± 0.01 ^{B d}	2.44 ± 0.45 ^c
	UVB15	0.61 ± 0.09 ^c	1.63 ± 0.19 ^c	0.60 ± 0.08 ^b	2.42 ± 0.01 ^{B d}	2.04 ± 0.31 ^b
5	CTRL	1.17 ± 0.09 ^{B c}	2.41 ± 0.02 ^{B bc}	0.95 ± 0.17 ^{AB ab}	3.24 ± 0.30 ^{B b}	2.34 ± 0.18 ^{B a}
	UVB5	1.14 ± 0.19 ^{B b}	3.22 ± 0.34 ^{A b}	0.55 ± 0.06 ^{B b}	4.71 ± 0.44 ^{A c}	2.28 ± 0.38 ^{B b}
	UVB10	1.74 ± 0.15 ^{A b}	3.51 ± 0.01 ^{A c}	1.00 ± 0.17 ^{AB bc}	4.67 ± 0.74 ^{A c}	3.49 ± 0.30 ^{A ab}
	UVB15	1.80 ± 0.34 ^{A b}	3.47 ± 0.15 ^{A b}	1.10 ± 0.32 ^{A b}	5.26 ± 0.07 ^{A c}	3.60 ± 0.69 ^{A a}
7	CTRL	2.14 ± 0.34 ^{B b}	3.73 ± 0.77 ^{ab}	1.38 ± 0.17 ^a	6.42 ± 2.05 ^a	3.06 ± 0.49 ^{B a}
	UVB5	2.50 ± 0.05 ^{AB a}	4.28 ± 0.24 ^a	1.42 ± 0.16 ^a	7.95 ± 0.14 ^b	3.57 ± 0.08 ^{AB a}
	UVB10	2.84 ± 0.24 ^{A a}	4.32 ± 0.19 ^b	1.93 ± 0.30 ^a	8.05 ± 0.26 ^b	4.05 ± 0.34 ^{A a}
	UVB15	2.61 ± 0.24 ^{AB a}	4.05 ± 0.22 ^b	1.86 ± 0.42 ^a	7.81 ± 1.00 ^b	3.73 ± 0.35 ^{AB a}
10	CTRL	2.98 ± 0.42 ^a	5.18 ± 0.69 ^a	1.37 ± 0.18 ^a	5.27 ± 1.20 ^{B ab}	2.98 ± 0.42 ^a
	UVB5	2.66 ± 0.37 ^a	4.29 ± 0.42 ^a	1.65 ± 0.29 ^a	11.94 ± 0.08 ^{A a}	2.66 ± 0.37 ^{ab}
	UVB10	2.99 ± 0.12 ^a	5.20 ± 0.12 ^a	1.37 ± 0.20 ^b	11.66 ± 0.67 ^{A a}	2.99 ± 0.12 ^{bc}
	UVB15	3.13 ± 0.33 ^a	5.57 ± 0.79 ^a	1.30 ± 0.13 ^{ab}	12.32 ± 0.06 ^{A a}	3.13 ± 0.33 ^{ab}

H/R: Hypocotyl/Root. FW/DW: Fresh weigh/Dry weight. Different capital letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different treatments for the same sampling time. Different lowercase letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different sampling times for the same treatment. Absence of letters indicates that there are no significant differences (p<0.05).

Table 2. Individual and total phenolic content of UV-B treated (CTRL; 5; 10, and 15 kJ m⁻²) kale sprouts during 10 growing d at 20 °C in darkness and stored up to 10 d at 4 °C as a minimally processed product.

<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Day of analysis</i>	<i>Gallic acid hexoside I</i>	<i>Gallic acid</i>	<i>3-O-caffeoylquinic acid</i>	<i>4-O-caffeoylquinic acid</i>	<i>5-O-caffeoylquinic acid</i>	<i>1,2-diferuloyl-gentobiose</i>
Seed	0G	0.00±0.00 ^{e/d/g/f}	0.00±0.00 ^{f/l/f/e}	5.15±0.20 ^{a/a/a/a}	0.00±0.00 ^{d/d/e/e}	0.00±0.00 ^{f/e/e/f}	0.40±0.04 ^{e/d/f/e}
	3G	0.36±0.04 ^{B d}	0.70±0.05 ^e	4.06±0.26 ^b	0.00±0.00 ^{B d}	0.07±0.01 ^e	2.65±0.13 ^{AB b}
	5G	0.49±0.00 ^{B d}	1.07±0.06 ^{C de}	1.88±0.17 ^{A c}	0.21±0.00 ^c	0.10±0.00 ^{B d}	3.31±0.18 ^a
	7G	0.70±0.10 ^{B c}	1.44±0.08 ^{C cd}	1.09±0.12 ^{A d}	0.25±0.00 ^b	0.19±0.01 ^c	2.29±0.04 ^c
	10G/0S	0.80±0.08 ^{C c}	1.96±0.06 ^{C c}	0.41±0.10 ^{A ef}	0.24±0.01 ^{B bc}	0.19±0.01 ^{C c}	1.20±0.11 ^{AB d}
	10G+4S	1.03±0.03 ^{C b}	3.51±0.22 ^{B b}	0.80±0.09 ^{A de}	0.27±0.01 ^{B ab}	0.23±0.01 ^{C b}	1.21±0.06 ^{B d}
	10G+7S	1.29±0.08 ^{B a}	5.06±0.48 ^{A a}	0.36±0.06 ^f	0.30±0.03 ^a	0.26±0.03 ^{B a}	1.23±0.02 ^{A d}
UVB5	10G+10S	1.33±0.10 ^{B a}	5.41±0.25 ^{A a}	0.37±0.05 ^f	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.26±0.02 ^{B ab}	1.17±0.12 ^{B d}
	3G	0.46±0.03 ^{A c}	0.68±0.06 ^e	4.20±0.25 ^b	0.00±0.00 ^{B d}	0.07±0.00 ^d	2.96±0.18 ^{A a}
	5G	0.54±0.00 ^{B c}	1.41±0.08 ^{AB d}	0.94±0.05 ^{B c}	0.21±0.01 ^c	0.14±0.02 ^{A c}	3.15±0.22 ^a
	7G	1.13±0.10 ^{A b}	1.91±0.05 ^{B cd}	0.45±0.04 ^{B d}	0.25±0.01 ^{bc}	0.20±0.03 ^b	2.27±0.11 ^b
	10G/0S	1.20±0.12 ^{B b}	2.44±0.11 ^{AB c}	0.27±0.01 ^{AB d}	0.26±0.01 ^{B b}	0.23±0.01 ^{B b}	1.13±0.04 ^{AB c}
	10G+4S	2.37±0.24 ^{A a}	7.22±0.44 ^{A a}	0.34±0.03 ^{B d}	0.29±0.02 ^{B ab}	0.28±0.01 ^{B a}	0.93±0.02 ^{C c}
	10G+7S	2.32±0.18 ^{A a}	3.83±0.16 ^{B b}	0.35±0.05 ^d	0.32±0.04 ^a	0.28±0.02 ^{B a}	1.01±0.05 ^{B c}
UVB10	10G+10S	2.14±0.20 ^{A a}	3.85±0.28 ^{C b}	0.31±0.03 ^d	0.32±0.03 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^{B a}	0.83±0.05 ^{A c}
	3G	0.25±0.02 ^{C f}	0.67±0.03 ^e	4.26±0.19 ^b	0.00±0.00 ^{B e}	0.07±0.01 ^d	2.72±0.16 ^{AB b}
	5G	0.81±0.00 ^{A e}	1.49±0.05 ^{A d}	0.89±0.14 ^{B c}	0.21±0.00 ^d	0.15±0.02 ^{A c}	3.48±0.23 ^a
	7G	1.06±0.05 ^{A d}	1.71±0.18 ^{BC cd}	0.44±0.03 ^{B d}	0.25±0.01 ^c	0.21±0.01 ^b	2.22±0.09 ^c
	10G/0S	1.69±0.08 ^{A c}	2.23±0.16 ^{BC c}	0.32±0.03 ^{AB d}	0.28±0.01 ^{A c}	0.25±0.01 ^{A b}	1.24±0.14 ^{A de}
	10G+4S	1.78±0.16 ^{B bc}	7.19±0.39 ^{A a}	0.40±0.01 ^{B d}	0.38±0.01 ^{A a}	0.36±0.03 ^{A a}	1.48±0.10 ^{A d}
	10G+7S	2.38±0.04 ^{A a}	4.26±0.30 ^{AB b}	0.33±0.01 ^d	0.35±0.03 ^{ab}	0.34±0.02 ^{A a}	1.13±0.07 ^{AB de}
UVB15	10G+10S	1.91±0.06 ^{A b}	4.08±0.08 ^{BC b}	0.31±0.02 ^d	0.34±0.02 ^b	0.32±0.02 ^{A a}	0.93±0.08 ^{A e}
	3G	0.29±0.02 ^{BC e}	0.73±0.04 ^d	4.34±0.42 ^b	0.22±0.00 ^{A cd}	0.08±0.02 ^e	2.43±0.08 ^{B b}
	5G	0.81±0.12 ^{A d}	1.24±0.07 ^{BC d}	0.76±0.04 ^{B c}	0.21±0.01 ^d	0.12±0.00 ^{AB d}	3.59±0.03 ^a
	7G	1.28±0.12 ^{A c}	2.36±0.21 ^{A c}	0.41±0.03 ^{B cd}	0.24±0.01 ^c	0.21±0.01 ^c	2.15±0.25 ^b
	10G/0S	1.87±0.02 ^{A b}	2.65±0.11 ^{A c}	0.24±0.03 ^{B d}	0.24±0.00 ^{B c}	0.22±0.01 ^{B c}	0.95±0.05 ^{B d}
	10G+4S	1.71±0.16 ^{B b}	7.07±0.30 ^{A a}	0.40±0.06 ^{B cd}	0.38±0.02 ^{A a}	0.40±0.02 ^{A a}	1.64±0.14 ^{A c}
	10G+7S	2.41±0.10 ^{A a}	4.43±0.26 ^{AB b}	0.31±0.02 ^{cd}	0.35±0.01 ^{ab}	0.36±0.02 ^{A b}	1.00±0.07 ^{B d}
10G+10S	2.15±0.07 ^{A a}	4.73±0.34 ^{B b}	0.29±0.02 ^{cd}	0.33±0.01 ^b	0.33±0.02 ^{A b}	0.84±0.04 ^{A d}	

Continued Table 2.

<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Day of analysis*</i>	<i>Caffeic acid</i>	<i>Caffeic acid derivative</i>	<i>Hydroxycinnamic acid</i>	<i>Kaempferol-3-diglucoside-7-glucoside</i>	<i>Kaempferol-3-sinapoyl-7-diglucoside</i>	<i>Total phenolic content (g kg⁻¹ DW)</i>	
Seed	0G	0.0±0.0 ^{f/f/e/e}	38.2±8.4 ^{e/e/e/f}	0.68±0.11 ^{e/c/e/f}	2.2±0.5 ^{e/d/e/f}	0.45±0.00 ^{e/e/d/f}	8.9±0.8 ^{d/e/g/f}	
	3G	30.8±4.9 ^e	63.2±6.1 ^{cd}	1.17±0.06 ^{de}	9.3±0.6 ^{B de}	0.98±0.18 ^d	19.4±0.7 ^{B c}	
	5G	63.8±0.3 ^d	60.0±3.2 ^{B d}	1.73±0.22 ^{B d}	14.4±0.1 ^{B d}	1.23±0.01 ^{C d}	24.5±0.3 ^{C c}	
	7G	72.5±1.7 ^{cd}	86.6±7.2 ^{ab}	2.44±0.12 ^{B c}	31.1±1.7 ^c	1.92±0.28 ^c	41.5±1.2 ^{B b}	
	CTRL	10G/0S	78.7±7.0 ^{bc}	81.0±8.6 ^{bc}	2.58±0.39 ^{AB bc}	33.9±4.5 ^{B bc}	1.82±0.08 ^{C c}	43.2±5.1 ^{B b}
		10G+4S	90.9±2.2 ^{B ab}	84.4±1.0 ^{C b}	2.88±0.15 ^{B abc}	40.7±1.8 ^{B ab}	2.06±0.08 ^{D bc}	52.9±2.0 ^{C a}
		10G+7S	103.1±8.7 ^a	90.8±4.3 ^{B ab}	3.18±0.24 ^{ab}	47.6±5.1 ^a	2.29±0.07 ^{C b}	61.7±5.5 ^a
10G+10S		100.6±5.1 ^a	103.6±8.1 ^a	3.29±0.41 ^a	47.1±4.6 ^a	2.96±0.08 ^a	62.4±5.3 ^a	
UVB5	3G	31.2±4.6 ^e	63.3±1.3 ^d	1.27±0.15 ^b	11.3±0.8 ^{A c}	1.06±0.15 ^d	22.1±1.5 ^{A d}	
	5G	62.9±6.5 ^d	70.0±5.0 ^{AB d}	1.83±0.13 ^{B b}	21.9±2.9 ^{A b}	1.58±0.18 ^{B c}	31.8±3.3 ^{B c}	
	7G	78.8±4.4 ^c	93.6±2.5 ^{bc}	2.95±0.01 ^{A a}	38.0±1.6 ^a	2.59±0.18 ^b	50.0±2.0 ^{A b}	
	10G/0S	86.6±1.1 ^{bc}	90.3±4.5 ^c	2.99±0.24 ^{A a}	45.5±3.4 ^{A a}	2.96±0.09 ^{A ab}	57.1±3.6 ^{A ab}	
	10G+4S	124.2±3.9 ^{A a}	109.3±2.0 ^{A a}	3.13±0.09 ^{B a}	43.6±0.5 ^{B a}	3.13±0.03 ^{C a}	61.6±1.3 ^{B a}	
	10G+7S	99.5±9.3 ^b	117.7±4.0 ^{A a}	3.04±0.29 ^a	42.0±4.2 ^a	2.89±0.24 ^{B ab}	56.2±4.9 ^{ab}	
	10G+10S	88.7±7.3 ^{bc}	105.8±4.6 ^{ab}	2.85±0.37 ^a	39.8±4.2 ^a	3.26±0.14 ^a	53.9±4.7 ^{ab}	
UVB10	3G	26.1±0.1 ^d	58.1±2.2 ^d	1.14±0.09 ^e	9.4±0.1 ^{B e}	0.87±0.07 ^d	19.5±0.6 ^{AB f}	
	5G	70.8±2.6 ^c	78.4±5.3 ^{A c}	2.44±0.16 ^{A d}	26.0±1.8 ^{A d}	1.99±0.10 ^{A c}	37.6±2.2 ^{A e}	
	7G	76.1±1.9 ^c	89.7±8.1 ^{bc}	2.59±0.33 ^{AB d}	32.6±4.7 ^{cd}	2.28±0.40 ^c	43.5±5.2 ^{AB de}	
	10G/0S	82.1±6.1 ^c	90.0±4.0 ^{bc}	2.91±0.22 ^{AB cd}	37.3±3.5 ^{AB bc}	2.52±0.12 ^{B bc}	48.9±3.7 ^{AB cd}	
	10G+4S	134.0±7.1 ^{A a}	99.3±2.0 ^{B ab}	4.07±0.22 ^{A a}	51.9±3.7 ^{A a}	3.55±0.16 ^{B a}	71.3±4.0 ^{A a}	
	10G+7S	107.9±6.3 ^b	113.8±4.2 ^{A a}	3.58±0.27 ^{ab}	48.4±1.5 ^a	3.19±0.18 ^{AB a}	64.2±1.6 ^{ab}	
	10G+10S	95.9±6.5 ^b	108.7±4.8 ^a	3.25±0.30 ^{bc}	43.7±4.2 ^{ab}	3.05±0.21 ^{ab}	58.1±4.6 ^{bc}	
UVB15	3G	24.1±1.5 ^d	58.8±3.0 ^e	1.19±0.05 ^e	9.1±0.4 ^{B e}	0.92±0.05 ^e	19.4±0.9 ^{B e}	
	5G	67.4±4.0 ^c	66.9±6.9 ^{AB de}	2.36±0.08 ^{A d}	23.2±1.4 ^{A d}	1.78±0.08 ^{AB d}	34.2±1.7 ^{AB d}	
	7G	75.0±4.9 ^c	79.0±6.0 ^{cd}	3.06±0.15 ^{A c}	34.7±1.1 ^c	2.54±0.07 ^c	47.1±1.7 ^{AB c}	
	10G/0S	74.9±0.4 ^c	94.8±5.0 ^{bc}	2.23±0.16 ^{B d}	29.8±1.5 ^{B c}	2.10±0.16 ^{C d}	40.5±1.5 ^{B cd}	
	10G+4S	133.9±8.8 ^{A a}	98.0±6.7 ^{B b}	4.37±0.24 ^{A a}	54.2±4.1 ^{A a}	4.08±0.17 ^{A a}	74.5±4.4 ^{A a}	
	10G+7S	106.6±3.7 ^b	115.9±4.7 ^{A a}	3.56±0.07 ^b	46.8±1.9 ^b	3.40±0.22 ^{A b}	62.8±2.4 ^b	
	10G+10S	95.1±1.2 ^b	117.1±4.2 ^a	3.00±0.31 ^c	41.2±2.8 ^b	3.00±0.26 ^b	56.1±3.6 ^b	

*G= growing days at 20 °C in darkness; S= shelf-life days at 4 °C as a minimally processed product. Concentrations are reported as g gallic acid equivalents kg⁻¹ dw for gallic acid hexoside I and gallic acid; as g chlorogenic acid equivalents kg⁻¹ dw for 3-O-caffeoylquinic acid, 4-O-caffeoylquinic acid, 5-O-caffeoylquinic acid, and 1,2-diferuloyl-gentobiose; as mg caffeic acid equivalents kg⁻¹ dw for caffeic acid and caffeic acid derivative; as g hydroxycinnamic acid equivalents kg⁻¹ dw for hydroxycinnamic acid; and as g rutin equivalents kg⁻¹ dw for kaempferol-3-diglucoside-7-glucoside and kaempferol-3-sinapoyl-7-diglucoside. Different capital letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different treatments for the same sampling time. Different lowercase letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different sampling times for the same treatment. Absence of letters indicates that there are no significant differences (p<0.05).

Table 3. Glucosinolates content (g kg⁻¹ dw) of UV-B treated (CTRL; 5; 10, and 15 kJ m⁻²) kale sprouts during 10 growing d at 20 °C in darkness and stored up to 10 d at 4 °C as a minimally processed product.

Treatment	Day of analysis	Glucobrassicin-dsg	Progoitrin-dsg	Glucoraphanin-dsg	4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin-dsg	Glucoerucin-dsg	Glucobrassicin-dsg	4-methoxy-glucobrassicin-dsg	Neoglucobrassicin-dsg	Total glucosinolate content
Seed	0G	17.0 ± 3.1 ^{a/a/a/a}	1.0 ± 0.1 ^{ab/de/ab/ab}	43.0 ± 6.4 ^{a/a/ab/a}	37.2 ± 5.7 ^{a/a/ab/a}	16.2 ± 1.8 ^{ab/ab/bc/bc}	2.2 ± 0.2 ^{b/e/b/e}	0.6 ± 0.1 ^{c/b/d/f}	0.3 ± 0.0 ^{b/e/d/d}	117.4 ± 12.8 ^{-/e/b/c}
CTRL	3G	8.4 ± 0.6 ^b	1.3 ± 0.1 ^a	32.6 ± 1.2 ^{ab}	25.1 ± 2.5 ^{ab}	11.6 ± 1.6 ^b	5.1 ± 1.0 ^b	6.6 ± 0.4 ^{A b}	3.7 ± 0.8 ^b	94.4 ± 12.5
	5G	10.3 ± 1.7 ^{B b}	1.4 ± 0.1 ^{A a}	32.7 ± 1.2 ^{B ab}	25.2 ± 2.5 ^{B ab}	17.8 ± 1.6 ^a	12.7 ± 1.3 ^a	10.3 ± 1.3 ^{ab}	9.0 ± 0.9 ^{B a}	119.4 ± 15.9 ^C
	7G	9.1 ± 0.4 ^b	1.1 ± 0.2 ^{ab}	26.7 ± 1.1 ^{B b}	28.6 ± 2.9 ^{ab}	14.2 ± 0.2 ^{C ab}	12.2 ± 1.3 ^a	10.0 ± 1.0 ^{B ab}	11.8 ± 1.3 ^{C a}	113.7 ± 10.8 ^B
	10G/0S	7.9 ± 0.8 ^{B b}	1.3 ± 0.1 ^{A a}	32.8 ± 2.5 ^{B ab}	29.3 ± 2.9 ^{A ab}	14.3 ± 0.4 ^{B ab}	13.5 ± 0.9 ^{A a}	14.5 ± 1.0 ^{AB a}	12.3 ± 0.3 ^{B a}	125.9 ± 1.4 ^{BC}
	10G+4S	7.3 ± 0.3 ^b	1.0 ± 0.1 ^{ab}	24.0 ± 2.3 ^b	27.9 ± 0.6 ^{ab}	14.1 ± 1.5 ^{ab}	11.2 ± 1.9 ^a	13.3 ± 1.6 ^{B a}	10.4 ± 1.6 ^a	110.1 ± 18.8
UVB5	10G+7S	7.3 ± 1.3 ^{B b}	1.1 ± 0.2 ^{ab}	32.2 ± 3.5 ^{ab}	32.8 ± 2.8 ^{AB ab}	15.7 ± 1.2 ^{B ab}	12.7 ± 0.8 ^a	10.1 ± 0.6 ^{C ab}	10.0 ± 1.2 ^{B a}	121.8 ± 5.3 ^B
	10G+10S	8.3 ± 1.2 ^{AB b}	0.8 ± 0.1 ^b	23.2 ± 2.5 ^{AB b}	19.5 ± 2.3 ^{A b}	13.0 ± 1.4 ^{AB ab}	12.3 ± 1.4 ^a	11.1 ± 1.3 ^{ab}	10.4 ± 2.2 ^{AB a}	98.6 ± 16.6 ^{AB}
	3G	13.4 ± 2.8 ^{ab}	1.7 ± 0.2 ^a	37.8 ± 3.8 ^{ab}	29.8 ± 2.7 ^a	14.9 ± 1.5 ^{ab}	6.1 ± 0.9 ^d	3.4 ± 0.4 ^{B b}	5.9 ± 1.1 ^d	123 ± 20.1 ^{bc}
	5G	15.1 ± 1.0 ^{A a}	1.5 ± 0.1 ^{AB ab}	43.7 ± 4.3 ^{A a}	36.9 ± 3.5 ^{AB a}	19.4 ± 1.5 ^{ab}	13.1 ± 0.8 ^{ab}	13.9 ± 1.2 ^a	23.8 ± 1.5 ^{A a}	167.4 ± 11.9 ^{AB a}
	7G	14.3 ± 1.6 ^{ab}	1.3 ± 0.1 ^{bc}	39.8 ± 2.2 ^{B ab}	35.5 ± 3.1 ^a	20.3 ± 0.4 ^{AB a}	13.7 ± 1.6 ^a	15.3 ± 1.8 ^{B a}	25.1 ± 1.7 ^{B a}	165.4 ± 9.5 ^{A a}
UVB10	10G/0S	7.4 ± 1.0 ^{B c}	0.8 ± 0.1 ^{B d}	24.4 ± 3.7 ^{B cd}	21.4 ± 5.1 ^{AB b}	13.7 ± 1.1 ^{B b}	10.6 ± 0.5 ^{B bc}	13.0 ± 1.2 ^{B a}	13.3 ± 1.3 ^{B b}	104.6 ± 16.5 ^{C c}
	10G+4S	8.9 ± 1.0 ^{bc}	1.0 ± 0.0 ^{cde}	29.6 ± 2.0 ^{bc}	20.7 ± 2.5 ^b	15.5 ± 1.4 ^{ab}	11.6 ± 0.5 ^{abc}	14.7 ± 1.2 ^{AB a}	11.0 ± 1.2 ^{bc}	113.0 ± 7.0 ^c
	10G+7S	13.2 ± 0.7 ^{A ab}	1.3 ± 0.1 ^{bcd}	37.8 ± 0.3 ^{ab}	33.8 ± 2.5 ^{A a}	19.5 ± 0.4 ^{AB ab}	13.0 ± 1.3 ^{abc}	14.7 ± 1.8 ^{B a}	24.7 ± 1.5 ^{A a}	158.1 ± 4.8 ^{A ab}
	10G+10S	5.6 ± 1.0 ^{B c}	0.5 ± 0.1 ^f	13.5 ± 0.9 ^{B d}	9.9 ± 1.3 ^{B c}	6.8 ± 0.6 ^{B c}	10.0 ± 0.3 ^c	11.3 ± 1.2 ^a	7.0 ± 1.0 ^{B cd}	65.0 ± 12.1 ^{B d}
	3G	12.0 ± 1.5 ^{ab}	1.4 ± 0.2 ^a	36.8 ± 4.3 ^{abc}	31.5 ± 3.1 ^{ab}	14.2 ± 1.2 ^{bc}	5.1 ± 1.0 ^b	6.6 ± 0.5 ^{A cd}	4.1 ± 1.0 ^d	111.8 ± 14.2 ^b
UVB15	5G	15.2 ± 0.9 ^{A ab}	1.6 ± 0.2 ^{AB a}	44.8 ± 2.2 ^{A a}	40.3 ± 4.1 ^{AB a}	20.2 ± 0.1 ^{ab}	13.2 ± 1.3 ^a	12.6 ± 2.0 ^c	24.3 ± 1.6 ^{A b}	172.2 ± 7.8 ^{A a}
	7G	14.6 ± 0.6 ^{ab}	1.4 ± 0.3 ^a	47.5 ± 4.6 ^{A a}	32.9 ± 3.2 ^{ab}	19.3 ± 0.5 ^{B ab}	14.0 ± 1.5 ^a	27.0 ± 1.8 ^{A a}	24.8 ± 2.3 ^{B b}	181.6 ± 18.7 ^{A a}
	10G/0S	13.1 ± 0.8 ^{A ab}	1.1 ± 0.2 ^{AB ab}	46.2 ± 4.5 ^{A a}	19.7 ± 1.2 ^{AB c}	25.2 ± 2.1 ^{A a}	13.5 ± 0.9 ^{A a}	20.1 ± 2.2 ^{A b}	35.3 ± 1.4 ^{A a}	174.2 ± 8.7 ^{A a}
	10G+4S	9.1 ± 0.5 ^b	1.0 ± 0.1 ^{ab}	28.8 ± 4.2 ^{bc}	19.5 ± 1.3 ^c	16.1 ± 1.3 ^{bc}	12.0 ± 1.4 ^a	19.3 ± 1.1 ^{A b}	11.3 ± 1.2 ^c	116.9 ± 17.0 ^b
	10G+7S	12.6 ± 0.9 ^{A ab}	1.3 ± 0.1 ^{ab}	36.5 ± 3.3 ^{abc}	27.7 ± 1.1 ^{B bc}	18.9 ± 1.6 ^{AB ab}	13.6 ± 0.0 ^a	29.0 ± 0.6 ^{A a}	23.9 ± 1.9 ^{A b}	163.6 ± 8.1 ^{A a}
10G+10S	9.6 ± 2.6 ^{AB b}	0.7 ± 0.1 ^b	30.3 ± 3.4 ^{A c}	17.6 ± 1.7 ^{AB c}	11.7 ± 1.3 ^{AB c}	10.8 ± 1.0 ^a	12.5 ± 1.2 ^c	10.6 ± 0.0 ^{AB c}	100.2 ± 15.3 ^{AB b}	
UVB15	3G	10.5 ± 1.1 ^b	1.4 ± 0.2 ^a	31.5 ± 2.2 ^{ab}	31.5 ± 3.1 ^{ab}	11.7 ± 1.7 ^c	5.1 ± 1.0 ^{de}	5.1 ± 0.9 ^{AB ef}	4.1 ± 1.1 ^d	100.9 ± 21.6 ^c
	5G	13.5 ± 0.3 ^{A ab}	1.2 ± 0.2 ^{B ab}	40.4 ± 0.6 ^{AB a}	31.4 ± 3.4 ^{AB ab}	19.2 ± 0.5 ^{ab}	10.3 ± 1.3 ^{bc}	9.6 ± 1.1 ^{de}	13.2 ± 1.5 ^{B c}	138.8 ± 13.3 ^{BC abc}
	7G	13.9 ± 2.0 ^{ab}	1.2 ± 0.1 ^{ab}	37.4 ± 4.6 ^{AB ab}	31.3 ± 0.7 ^{ab}	23.0 ± 2.2 ^{A a}	14.8 ± 2.0 ^a	22.9 ± 2.3 ^{A a}	32.1 ± 1.1 ^{A ab}	176.6 ± 15.2 ^{A a}
	10G/0S	10.1 ± 1.0 ^{AB b}	1.0 ± 0.1 ^{AB ab}	26.4 ± 4.4 ^{B b}	15.6 ± 1.2 ^{B c}	18.0 ± 1.5 ^{B abc}	8.4 ± 0.8 ^{B cd}	20.7 ± 2.2 ^{A ab}	35.1 ± 3.1 ^{A a}	135.2 ± 11.3 ^{B bc}
	10G+4S	10.1 ± 0.1 ^b	1.1 ± 0.1 ^{ab}	30.8 ± 3.1 ^{ab}	21.7 ± 1.8 ^{bc}	16.2 ± 0.8 ^{bc}	11.4 ± 0.3 ^{abc}	15.8 ± 0.5 ^{AB bc}	11.56 ± 0.6 ^c	118.6 ± 5.5 ^{bc}
UVB15	10G+7S	12.9 ± 1.7 ^{A ab}	1.2 ± 0.1 ^{ab}	35.4 ± 2.8 ^{ab}	35.6 ± 1.6 ^{A a}	20.2 ± 2.4 ^{A ab}	12.5 ± 0.5 ^{ab}	14.6 ± 0.5 ^{B cd}	25.8 ± 1.6 ^{A b}	158.4 ± 10.1 ^{A ab}
	10G+10S	12.0 ± 2.8 ^{A ab}	0.6 ± 0.1 ^b	33.6 ± 4.9 ^{A ab}	15.9 ± 1.5 ^{AB c}	14.1 ± 1.1 ^{A bc}	9.9 ± 0.6 ^{bc}	12.4 ± 1.1 ^{cd}	11.4 ± 1.8 ^{A c}	110.0 ± 18.5 ^{A c}

G= growing days at 20 °C in darkness; S= shelf-life days at 4 °C as a minimally processed product. Different capital letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different treatments for the same sampling time. Different lowercase letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different sampling times for the same treatment. Absence of letters indicates that there are no significant differences (p<0.05).

Author contributions statement

Noelia Castillejo: Methodology; Formal analysis; Investigation; Writing – Original Draft.

Lorena Martínez-Zamora: Methodology; Formal analysis; Data curation; Investigation;

Writing – Original Draft. Francisco Artés–Hernández: Conceptualization; Resources;

Writing – Review & Editing; Supervision; Funding acquisition.

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. UHPLC chromatograms (shown at 320 nm) of identified phenolic compounds from methanol/water (80:20, v/v) extracts of kale seed (A) and kale sprouts treated with UV-B (0, 5, 10, and 15 kJ m⁻²) (B, C, D, and E, respectively) during 10 growing d at 20 °C in darkness and stored up to 10 d at 4 °C as a minimally processed product. Identified peaks are: (1) Gallic acid hexoside I, (2) Gallic acid, (3) 3-O-caffeoylquinic acid, (4) 4-O-caffeoylquinic acid, (5) 5-O-caffeoylquinic acid, (6) 1,2-diferuloyl-gentobiose, (7) caffeic acid, (8) caffeic acid derivative, (9) hydroxycinnamic acid, (10) Kaempferol-3-diglucoside-7-glucoside, and (11) Kaempferol-3-sinapoyl-7-diglucoside.

Figure 2. UHPLC chromatograms (shown at 227 nm) of identified glucosinolates from ethanol/water (70:30, v/v) extracts of kale seed (A) and kale sprouts treated with UV-B (0, 5, 10, and 15 kJ m⁻²) (B, C, D, and E, respectively) during 10 growing d at 20 °C in darkness and stored up to 10 d at 4 °C as a minimally processed product. Identified peaks are: (1) Glucoiberin, (2) Progoitrin, (3) Glucoraphanin, (4) 4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin, (5) Glucoerucin, (6) Glucobrassicin, (7) 4-methoxy-glucobrassicin, and (8) Neoglucobrassicin.

Figure 3. Total phenolic content of kale sprouts treated with UV-B (CTRL, 5, 10, and 15 kJ m⁻²) during 10 growing d at 20 °C in darkness and stored up to 10 d at 4 °C as a minimally processed product. Different capital letters indicate significant differences among treatments at $p < 0.05$ based on Tukey's test. Different lowercase letters indicate significant differences among time of analysis of the same treatment at $p < 0.05$ based on Tukey's test.

Figure 4. Total antioxidant activity measured by DPPH (A) and FRAP (B) of kale sprouts treated with UV-B (CTRL, 5, 10, and 15 kJ m⁻²) during 10 growing d at 20 °C and 10 d stored at 4 °C. Different capital letters indicate significant differences among treatments

at $p < 0.05$ based on Tukey's test. Different lowercase letters indicate significant differences among time of analysis of the same treatment at $p < 0.05$ based on Tukey's test.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: